

“Information Literacy among Lecturers in Colleges-A Study on Mangalore University Colleges”

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Abstract: *"A little knowledge that acts is worth infinitely more than much knowledge that is idle." –Khalil Gibran*

This paper examined information literacy skills among lecturers of Under graduation colleges which are comes under Mangalore University, Karnataka. The descriptive survey design was adopted for the study and the samples were selected randomly for the study. 100 questionnaires were retrieved and used for the study. Simple percentage and frequency count statistical tool was used to analyze the data. The study found out that ability to use information effectively to accomplish a task, ability to recognize the needed information, ability to access the needed information effectively and efficiently and ability to evaluate information critically are the information literacy skills possessed by some of the lecturers in Mangalore University.

Key Words: *Information Literacy, Information literacy level, Usage.*

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I. Introduction

According to the Association of College and Research Libraries' (ACRL, 2000), "Information literacy is a set of abilities requiring individuals to recognize when information is needed and have the ability to locate, evaluate, and use effectively the needed information". The same document points out those information literacy skills are created to reinforce the above abilities. The skills of recognizing, locating, identifying, retrieving and evaluating information can be included as part of the teaching of an existing course or constitute an independent course in the curriculum.

In a digital world where the amount of information doubles every two years, everyone needs to evaluate the resources carefully and determine how to use relevant information to solve the problems and make wise decisions. The information society calls people to become information literate which means that they should not only be able to recognize when information is needed but also be able to identify, locate, evaluate and use effectively information needed for decision making or fulfilling different goals. Information Literacy (IL) is increasingly important in the present context of the information explosion and concomitant uncertainty about its authenticity, validity, and reliability. Information literacy enables the readers to master content and give them the confidence to proceed with investigation be self reliant and have a sense of being in control of their learning.

Objectives of the Study:

1. To identify the information needs, types of sources use on internet, purpose of seeking information of the lecturers.
2. To know the problems faced by respondents while looking for information.
3. To give suggestions based on the study.

Hypothesis:

1. H_0 : There is no significant relationship between Gender and Information literacy level.
2. H_0 : There is no significant relationship between Age and convenient in using electronic source.

II. Methodology

The present study is based on the survey method using a structured questionnaire and set the scope of the present study limited to the awareness of Information Literacy Concept among lecturers of under graduation colleges which are comes under Mangalore University. The questionnaire has been devised keeping in view the objectives of the study.

Limitations:

1. Time limitation
2. Limited coverage(Only Mangalore University Under graduation Colleges)

Data analysis and Interpretation:

In the era of information technology the concept of classroom teaching has also been changed and the students are conversion which the use of e-mail and internet facilities. The teaching of subject by the lecturers restricted. The text book may not the expected by the student and the teachers are also expected to improve their knowledge skill and presentation to attract students towards classroom. If the care is not taken by the lecturers will be the root cause of going students away from the classrooms. With this concept the present study has been planned.

Demographic Profile of the Respondent:

Here researcher tries to get data from different type of respondents. Respondents distributed into two type of Gender that is male and female and three types of age group that is between 20-30, between 30-40 and above 40 years.

Table No.1: Showing the demographic profile of the respondents

		No. of Respondents	Total	Percentage %
1. Gender	Male	43	100	43%
	Female	57		57%
2. Age group	Between 20-30	76	100	76%
	Between 30-40	15		15%
	Above 40	9		9%

From the above table it is clear that majority respondents are females (57%) and males (43%). Here ages are grouped into three and from this study we come to know that majority respondent (76%) are come under age group of between 20-30. That means in Mangalore university degree colleges consists highest number of young faculties. 15% of the respondents are come under age group of 30-40 and 9% of respondents are above 40 year.

Source of Information:

Here researcher asked respondents while they seeking information which source of information they usually refers. For that questions respondents answered properly. The following is the table showing distribution.

Table No.2: Showing the Source of Information

SL.No	Source	Frequency	Percentage
1	Discussion with colleagues	81	81%
2	Face to face discussion.	43	43%
3	Consult knowledgeable	62	62%
4	Consult supervisor	14	14%
5	Discussion with librarian or reference staff of your library	5	5%
6	Discussion with librarian or reference of other library	5	5%
7	Abstracting journal.	24	24%
8	Library catalogue	14	14%
9	Review articles	14	14%
10	Any other (please mention)	14	14%

The respondents under study were classified according to the sources of information seeking the frequency distribution indicated that the 81% of the respondents as preferred for discussion with colleagues. In the field of teaching & research to face to face discussion should have most unique importance however the respondents are relatively least interested in face to face discussion, 43% respondents as preferred for face to face discussion. 62% of the respondents consult persons who are knowledgeable in the seeking area. Very few lecturers (5%) seeking information from librarian.

Purpose of Information Seeking:

Information seeking behavior will be fruitful with has destination that is the purpose for which is required. If the users do not have any specific purpose of collecting purpose that the information collected a scare therefore the respondents were asked the purpose for which the information is seeking in all twelve purposes were narrated and the opinions of the respondents were recorded. Following table show the same.

Table No.3: Showing the Purpose of Information Seeking:

SL.No	Purpose	Frequency	Percentage
1	For prepare class lectures	90	90%
2	For understand knowledge	81	81%
3	For doing research work.	19	19%
4	For writing paper and presenting paper	33	33%
5	For doing Ph. D.	24	24%
6	For guiding researchers.	10	10%
7	Prepare the class-notes.	29	29%
8	General awareness	62	62%
9	For entertainment	14	14%
10	Observation & experiments	5	5%
11	Discussion	10	10%
12	Reading / thinking purpose	10	10%

From the above table researcher come to know that 90% of the respondents agreed that the main purpose of Information seeking are for class preparation and 81% of the respondents have opinion that they look information for understand knowledge or concept.62% of the respondents are look for information for the purpose of general awareness.33% respondents are look information for writing paper and presenting paper and 24% of the respondents look information for the purpose of doing Ph.D.

✚ Type of material seek in library

It is general opinion that lecturers are book worm, they always prefer books for accessing knowledge. For that purpose researcher asked respondents about which type of material seek in library for knowledge gaining. Following is the response of respondents,

Table 4 : Showing the Type of material seek in library

SL.No	Type of Material	Frequency	Percentage
1	Text books	81	81%
2	Periodicals / journals	57	57%
3	News papers	67	67%
4	Exhibition	10	10%
5	Govt. publication	10	10%
6	Reference books	71	71%
7	Pamphlets	5	5%
8	General books	29	29%
9	Patents/ Reports	00	00%
10	Thesis / Research reports	19	19%
11	Review articles	00	00%
12	Audio/ Video/ DVD.	14	14%
13	Email	5	5%
14	Meeting/ Seminar/ Conference/ Workshops	10	10%
15	Internet.	52	52%
16	Any other	00	00%

From the above table it is clear that 81% of the respondents refer books in library and 67% respondents look for News paper for updating current affairs.71% of the respondents refer reference book in library. Recent days most of the people look for Internet source for getting information because of easy access. Here 52% of the respondents look for Internet based source.

✚ Problems while Seeking material

Every one go for library with mind set of getting information they look for but some time they unable to get information as they needed due to some problems. There for researcher asked respondents about problems faced by respondents when they seeking materi

Table 5: Problems while Seeking material

Sl.No.	Problems	Frequency	Percentage
1	Non availability of material.	71	71%
2	Library staff is unwilling for service.	05	5%
3	Information sources are so far located.	19	19%
4	Lack of time	57	57%
5	Poor knowledge regarding use of Catalogue.	14	14%
6	Difficulty in understanding English language.	05	5%
7	Incomplete information materials.	24	24%
8	Lack of knowledge in using the library	10	10%
9	Information is scattered	19	19%
10	Information scattered in too many sources	05	5%
11	Information is too vast	05	5%
12	Some of the information materials are old .	38	38%
13	Latest information sources are not available	43	43%
14	Any other.	00	00%

From the above table majority of the respondents (71%) faced Non-availability of material when they look for information.57% of the respondents faced Lack of time to look for material.43% of the respondents unable to get latest information sources are not available.10% of respondents have lack of knowledge in using the library.

✚ Find the Information

The desire information is retrieved or not becomes always a question of interest. If we are able in retrieving the desire information, we are place at comfortable position. Non retrieval Desire information brings the uses embracing position us that the task is not completed. With this views the uses opinion on the retrieval of information were recorded & the presented in this following table.

Table No.6: Availability of Looking Information

Sl.No.	Looking Information	Frequency	Percentage
1	Yes	19	19%
2	No	05	5%
3	Partially	76	76%

From the above table it is clear that majority of the respondents (76%) are opinions that they got only partial information when they seek information from the library. Only 5% of the respondents are unable to get information from the library. Only 19% of the respondents were got full information which they look for.

✚ Keep abreast of current developments

Teacher is said to be students through his/ her life as his required & expected to learn & grasp the recent development in his / her subject. Therefore teacher is supposed to keep abreast of current development in the subject fields. Therefore researcher asked the respondents about how they keep abreast of current developments. The following table shows the response of the respondents.

Table No.7: Keep abreast of current developments

Sl.No.	Source	Frequency	Percentage
1	Current issue journals	43	43%
2	Online journals	57	57%
3	Attendance at conference.	24	24%
4	Internet/ e-mail alert	52	52%
5	Through services from library as CAS &SDI	05	5%
6	Personal communication	52	52%
7	Any other.	05	5%

From the above table researchers find that 43% respondents refer online journals for enhancing their knowledge in current issues. Now a day every information we can get through internet. Here 52% of the respondents are opinions that they increase their knowledge by internet.

✚ Prefer to reference materials (print or electronic Copy)

Modern world most prefer in paperless transaction therefore researcher asked respondents about preference in reference material whether in print copy (Hard copy) or Electronic copy (Soft copy).For that question they responded as follows,

Table No.8: Prefer to reference materials

Sl.No	Material	Frequency	Percentage
1	Print copy	19	19%
2	Electronic copy	19	19%
3	Both-Print & electronic copy	62	62%

From the above table it is clear that majority of respondents 62% have opinions that they refer both Print and electronic copy as a reference material.19% of the respondents refer print copy and 19% of the respondents refer electronic copy.

✚ Electronic sources make it easier or more difficult to gather information

Most of the people opt the way which is convenient to them. Therefore the researcher asked the respondents about level of convenience in using electronic source.

Table No.9: Convenience of Electronic source

Sl.No.	Particular	Frequency	Percentage
1	Easier	70	70%
2	About the Same	24	24%
3	More difficult	06	6%

From the above table we come to know that majority of the respondents (70%) agreed that they feel easier when they using electronic source.24% of the respondents feel that there is neither easier nor difficult to them for using electronic source when compared to the print copy.

Hypothesis Testing:

1. **H₀: There is no significant relationship between Gender and Information literacy level.**

H₁: There is significant relationship between Gender and Information literacy level.

		Answer of the respondents		
		Answered correctly	Answered wrongly	Total
Gender	Male	33	10	43
	Female	29	28	57
	Total	62	38	100

Analysis: Hypothesis are solved with help chi-square test

	There is no significant relationship between Gender and Info		
	Answered correctly	Answered wrongly	
Male	33 <i>26.66</i> (1.51)	10 <i>16.34</i> (2.46)	43
Female	29 <i>35.34</i> (1.14)	28 <i>21.66</i> (1.86)	57
	62	38	100

$\chi^2 = 6.961, \quad df = 1, \quad \chi^2/df = 6.96, \quad P(\chi^2 > 6.961) = 0.0083$

Note: Expected values are displayed in *italics* individual χ^2 values are displayed in (parentheses)

Interpretation:

Here calculated value (6.961) is less than table value (7.879) at 5% significant level. So here Null hypothesis should be accepted and alternative hypothesis is rejected. Therefore we can say that there is no significant relationship between information literacy level and gender of the respondents. It means awareness of library information distributed among gender irrationally.

2. H₀: There is no significant relationship between age and convenient in using electronic source.

H₁: There is significant relationship between age and convenient in using electronic source.

		Convenience Level			Total
		Easier	About the Same	More Difficult	
Age Group	20-30	57	14	5	76
	30-40	10	5	0	15
	40 & Above	3	5	1	9
Total		70	24	6	100

Analysis: Hypothesis are solved with help chi-square test

		Convenience Level			
		Easier	About the Same	More Difficult	
Age Group	20-30	57 <i>53.20</i> (0.27)	14 <i>18.24</i> (0.99)	5 <i>4.56</i> (0.04)	76
	30-40	10 <i>10.50</i> (0.02)	5 <i>3.60</i> (0.54)	0 <i>0.90</i> (0.90)	15
	40 & Above	3 <i>6.30</i> (1.73)	5 <i>2.16</i> (3.73)	1 <i>0.54</i> (0.39)	9
Total		70	24	6	100

$$\chi^2 = 8.622, \quad df = 4, \quad \chi^2/df = 2.16, \quad P(\chi^2 > 8.622) = 0.0713$$

Note: Expected values are displayed in *italics* individual χ^2 values are displayed in (parentheses)

Interpretation:

Here calculated value (8.622) is less than table value (14.860) at 5% significant level. So here Null hypothesis should be accepted and alternative hypothesis is rejected. Therefore we can say that there is no significant relationship between age group and convenience in using electronic source among respondents. It means even older generation also getting convenient in using electronic source.

III. Findings of The Study

- Majority of the lecturers of Mangalore University are age group between 20-30 years.
- There is highest number of female faculty in Mangalore university degree colleges.
- Majority of the respondents (81%) are discuss with colleagues in order to get information and 62% of the respondents refer knowledgeable persons to gain knowledge.
- Majority of the respondents (90%) agreed that they seek information for the purpose of class preparation and 81% of the respondents seek information for better understanding of particular concept.
- Majority of the respondents (81%) of the respondents refer Text book for accessing information.
- The main problems faced by respondents while they look for information is non availability of material and lack of time.
- Majority of the respondents (76%) opinions that they get partial information when search for information.
- Majority of the respondents (57%) read online journal and 52% of the respondents browse Internet source for updating current issues.
- There is no relationship between gender of the respondents and their information literacy level.
- There is no relationship between age of the respondents and convenient level in usinf electronic sources.

IV. Suggestions

- ❖ The Progress of our nation depends on research. Faculties have always sought information for their teaching purpose. Today all types of information are available on the Net, so college library should enrich its collection be it Net or traditional sources.

- ❖ Internet is the most popular facility among the users. It is recommended that internet facility be made available at working place/Departments. For use of academic purpose.
- ❖ In the era of information technology no library is self sufficient to provide comprehensive services, to provide the needed information, hence resource sharing is must. Vast information, scattered information, old information material are main barriers for seeking information. It is suggested that librarian should inform faculty members about recent publication, and current information sources to keep them update in their field of knowledge this will save their time.

V. Conclusions

Information seeking is an important of our everyday lives. When faculty need information they go libraries, consults colleagues & web search engines & fulfilled their needs. The ultimate of any library service is to ensure that the select are able to access the information purpose from which they request it. This raises the need of information literacy to client with goal assisting client to identify and select relevant information using appropriate search strategies and being able to evaluate, organize and synthesis that information a meaningful presentation conducting various IL practice library environment.

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